

FEMINISM AS A LITERARY WORK

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Abstract. This article discusses the ideology of Feminism, which appeared in the Western world in the 18th century, and its roots. It is analyzed that feminism brings fundamental changes to women in politics, public sphere, workplace, family and cultural spheres, including art and literature. You can see that gender inequality has been a part of culture for hundreds of years, and as a result, in many cases, women have been oppressed and restricted in many ways. In the article, you can get acquainted with the general view of feminist ideas and values, as well as with feminist writers and writers who lived and created in different literary periods.

Keywords: feminism, gender inequality, gender-paradigm, emancipation.

АННОТАЦИЯ. В данной статье рассматривается идеология феминизма, возникшая в западном мире в 18 веке, и ее корни. Феминизм был проанализирован, чтобы вызвать фундаментальные изменения в женской политике, общественной сфере, на рабочем месте, в семье и культурных сферах, включая искусство и литературу. Вы можете видеть, что гендерное неравенство было частью культуры на протяжении сотен лет, и в результате во многих случаях женщины были сильно угнетены и ограничены во многих отношениях. В статье можно познакомиться с общим взглядом на феминистские идеи и ценности, а также с писателями-феминистками и писательницами, жившими и творившими в разные литературные периоды.

Ключевые слова: феминизм, гендер-парадигма, гендерное неравенство, эмансипация.

During the course of a person's life, he often encounters ideas, values, and experiences that have the power of mental and physical influence. Sometimes such experiences are reflected in society in various ways. In this way, the literature of the period appears as a mirror of various aspects of human life. Literature is a set of knowledge about human life, which is unique in terms of expressing the existence of a person in this life, the realities of the time, and his direct relationship to the processes taking place in time and space. Although it is difficult to analyze human life through literary works, it is easy to describe. There are many questions that have been searching for a solution for many times, and even in the present time, the solution has not been found, and many writers and Another topic that has caused intense debate among writers is the topic of gender inequality based on the ideas of feminism. Literature takes into account how it can be manifested while shaping human life on the basis of its values. The created works differ not only in terms of subject matter, but also in terms of genre. You can see and compare how the ideas of feminism and the concept of gender inequality occurred through works created in different literary genres such as prose, poetry,

drama and film. Gender inequality has been a part of culture for hundreds of years, and has often resulted in the oppression of women. In terms of gender inequality, men's advantage is increased, and women's rights and freedoms should be limited. This idea is part of the hegemonic structure, which is often called the "gender-paradigm" is called Artificial inequalities between men and women are still created in some cultures around the world.

There are different opinions about who introduced the term feminism to modern science. Researchers O. Voronina and V. Uspenskaya put forward the idea that the phrase feminism was used by the French writer Charles Furue at the end of the 18th century. Feminist termin is the fiction of the distant past, the thoughts and aspirations of female characters are reflected in the conflict between the traditional male and patriarchal society with the desire for self-control in women. In these works, the non-traditional female characters were severely criticized, rejected and ridiculed in the western world. The roots of the ideology of feminism by the end of the 18th century, it began to spread among society. "Protection of Women's Rights" by the writer Mary Wollstonecraft, who is famous as the basis of feminism and covered this topic in her works (1792), shows women's strong views on political and moral issues. It was not until the twentieth century, more than a hundred years later, that women began to take advantage of some of the opportunities of the long-running feminist movement for basic human rights. Feminism has led to radical changes in women's activities in politics, the public sphere, the workplace, the family, and cultural spheres, including art and literature. Especially in fiction, women's voices, which had faded before, began to resound.

At the end of the 17th century, women began to publish their works in the field of literature. Aphra Behn (1640-1689) in his "Oroonoko" or, "The Story of a Royal Slave"(1688) published a work known as This novel was the first in the English language to sympathize with the plight of female slaves.

The origin of the theory of literary feminism

The term feminism was coined in the early 20th century by Virginia Woolf in her book A Room for One's Own (1929). This concept underwent a rapid development in the 1960s, combining modern cultural theory with an analytical model covering the social, political, and economic spheres. According to A. Taumn, the feminist movement in the Western world is based on several factors, namely:

- 1. Development of contraceptive methods that allow women to free themselves from male power;*
- 2. Political radicalization;*
- 3. Freedom movements;*
- 4. Secularization, decline of religious authority in all spheres of life;*
- 5. Development of education;*
- 6. Reaction to literary approaches that distance the work from social structures, such as new criticism and structuralism;*
- 7. Dissatisfaction with the theory and practice of orthodox Marxist ideology.*

As mentioned above, the liberation movement raises the feminist movement that wants to fight for women's rights, deconstruct the system of domination and hegemony, and engage in the conflict between weak groups and powerful groups. Feminist theories are closely related to class and racial conflicts, especially gender conflicts. Feminism is usually associated with emancipation, the movement of women to demand equal rights with men in

the political, economic, and socio-cultural spheres. At the end of the 20th century, especially in the West, it was one of the most important signs of feminism.

The nineteenth century was a golden age of creativity for women. During this period, several novels of Jane Austen (1775-1817) were published, based on the norms of manners, which, together with parodying the ridiculous activities of an innocent society, criticized unjust social rules. In novels such as *Sense and Sensibility* (1811), *Pride and Prejudice* (1813), *Mansfield Park* (1814), *Emma* (1816), *Persuasion* (1818), and *Sanditon* (1925), life's violence against women is limited, including reveals the environment, shameful situations, lameness in education.

Feminist fiction writer Kate Chopin's feministic work(1851-1904) "Awakening" (1899.) is considered a novel that many libraries have banned from storage. Due to the moral aspect of the work, violent attitudes towards women, and hostile criticism aimed at the hero's rejection of traditional oppressive attitudes towards his wife, his book was strictly banned even in the Missouri library of the writer's hometown of St. Louis.

1920, when women won the right to vote in the United States, another feminist artist Edith Wharton(1862-1937) came to the field. He gained popularity among the general public through his novel "The Age of Innocence". Although the work focused on society's unfair treatment of women, it made Edith Wharton the first woman to win the Pulitzer Prize for fiction in 1921.

At a time when Wharton's career was flourishing in the United States, an English feminist Virginia Woolf (1882-1941), (he was also an essayist and editor) also gained popularity. He began his creative career in 1915 with the novel "Journey", which was published as a result of seven years of research. As an early adult, Woolf studied Greek, an unusual subject for a young woman of her time, taught at a working women's college, did odd jobs for the suffrage movement and wrote a series of articles for the prestigious times. All these experiences began to revive her feminist ideas.

"Night and Day" (Day and Night) Woolf formed the trials of a young writer, characters who are not like her. The images of Catherine Hilbury and Mary Detchit, as well as the images of Rose Pargiter in the novel, created the image of the "New Woman" in English literature of the 20th century. In "Jacob's Room" and later, Woolf was very influential. She created "Miss Dalloway". Rejecting the traditional novel structure, Woolf analyzed post-World War I London society by shifting from her protagonist's point of view to Septimus Warren Smith's for twenty-four hours. Woolf's "To the Lighthouse", which is often studied by feminist critics, the work will serve as a work that creates an environment that is both relaxing and stimulating for young women which criticizes the social customs of Victoria.

In this work, Woolf uses metaphors to explore social injustices and comments on women's inability to express themselves freely. His metaphor about the fish creates a clear image of this idea: "He believes that in order for a woman to create, she should have her own means and a special place in society." The fact that women begin to have views that contradict the unwritten laws of society causes them to face a whirlwind of severe criticism among the community. Following the general rules, the woman loses her mind. Here Woolf describes the position of women in social life as follows: "Women and girls are like domestic flowers grown at home, they look at the outside world only from behind the window panes, they are reflected in the image of fighters for purity and, therefore, together with ignorance. This, of course, also exposes many weaknesses in the education of girls in the same Renaissance social

system. The political appearance of the work is directly related to this metaphor. With the emergence of such injustices began to be seen and the struggle against the restrictions imposed on women's intellectual potential began as a result of their limited opportunities compared to men.

Summary. Gender inequality is a global phenomenon that the problem which has its place in all eras, has passed through the layers of space and time, and is still looking for its complete solution, exists even in our modern age. Nevertheless, it is gratifying to highlight the participation of women in the political processes being conducted today. The current political processes and the attention paid to them are the fruits of their struggle for thousands of years. Literature is the most correct way to influence the human mind, therefore, all the works that illuminate the concept of feminism came into the world as works of art in the work of writers..

References:

- 1."Remembering Virginia Woolf, the woman who brought feminism to the fore". India Today. 25 January 2018. Retrieved 10 September 2021.
- 2.Woolf, Virginia, Mrs Dalloway, Oxford University Press, 2009.
- 3.Mary: A Fiction. London: Joseph Johnson, 1788.
- 4.Noel J. (1953). "Jane Austen in France". Nineteenth-Century Fiction.
- 5.Alexander, Christine and Juliet McMaster, eds. The Child Writer from Austen to Woolf. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2005.
6. Auerbach, Emily. Searching for Jane Austen. Madison: University of Wisconsin Press, 2004.
- 7.Brandt G. Philosophical anthropology of feminism. Nature's ginseng. SPb. 2006. S.109
- 8.Bryson W. Political theory of feminism. M., 2001. S. 150
- 9.Gender Kaleidoscope. Course Lecture/Pod. ed. M. M. Malysheva. - M., 2002.
10. Davlatova, M. X. Rabota nad videotekstam na zanyatiyakh English language. Teoriyaipraktikasovrmennoy nauki, 242-246.
11. Nasriyeva, G. (2023). ARTISTIC EXPRESSION AND INTERPRETATION OF IMAGES IN THE STORIES OF NAZAR ESHANKUL. B SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (T. 2, Выпуск 11, cc. 152–157). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10054335>
12. INTERPRETATION OF SOCIETY AND PERSONALITY THROUGH PICTURES IN NAZAR ESHONKUL'S WORKS Nasriyeva Guzal Zulfiddin qizi ISSN: 2776-1010 Volume 4, Issue 10, Oct. 2023
13. Kudratova Sitora Rashidovna. (2023). LINGUISTIC ISSUES IN TRANSLATION. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(02), 29–35. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue02-07>
14. Rashidovna, K. S. (2023). The Influence of Culture on Translation Activities. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND APPLIED LINGUISTICS, 2(2), 80–83.
15. Kudratova Sitora Rashidovna. (2023). PRAGMATIC DISCORDANCE OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK PHRASES IN THE EVENT OF SPEECH ACT. MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE, 2(10), 24–28. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8368922>

16. Davlatova M.H. Typology of expressive emotional lexical units (in English and Uzbek languages).// Ўзбекистонда илмий-амалий тадқиқотлар мавзусидаги конференция материаллари. №16. – Тошкент, 2020, – Б. 220-221.
17. Davlatova M.H. Resultative and causative meanings in English and Uzbek languages.// Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali. – Surxandaryo, 2022. – P. 297-302.
18. Davlatova M.H. Typology of expressive emotional and linguistic features.// International journal of literature and languages, № 11. 2022. – P. 65-69.
19. Davlatova M.H. Aspectual and lexical-semantic classification of verbs. JournalNX-A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal, 8(2). 2022. – P. 116-121.
20. Davlatova M.H. On the interrelationship of resultative and causative meanings.// World Bulletin of Public Health № 9. 2022. – P. 212-215.
21. Mahmudova Dildora Murodilloyevna. (2023). CORPORA AND LITERATURE. Academia Repository, 4(11), 159–166. Retrieved from <https://academiarepo.org/index.php/1/article/view/186>
22. Mahmudova, D. (2023). CORPUS LINGUISTICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(23), 104-106.
23. Mahmudova, D. (2023). CORPUS LINGUISTICS. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(23), 104-106.
24. Fayzulloyevna, N. M., & Rustamovna, B. N. (2023). EXPRESSIVE FUNCTION OF ENGLISH ARGOT IN A LITERARY TEXT. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(05), 96-102.
25. Fayzulloyevna, N. M., & Rashidovna, B. Z. (2023). PHONOSTYLISTICS IS THE SCIENCE OF STUDYING THE SOUND COMPOSITION OF LITERARY TEXT. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(05), 115-120.
26. Fayzulloyevna, N. M. (2023). CATEGORY OF TENSION IN JD SALINGER'S WORKS. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(05), 128-133.
27. Fayzulloyevna, N. M. (2023). DIFFICULTIES IN TRANSLATING ARCHAISMS AND HISTORICISMS. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(10), 11-18.
28. Habibova, M. N. (2021). Jorjina Houellning "Queen of the desert" biografik asarida gertruda Bell timsoli tasviri. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(2), 770-778.
29. Habibova, M. N. (2021). The theme feminism in the epistolary novels in modern times. ISJ Theoretical & Applied Science, 11(103), 1101-1105.
30. Habibova, M. N. (2022). THE HISTORY OF THE RUSSIAN EPISTOLARY NOVEL IN EIGHTEENTH CENTURY. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCES, PHILOSOPHY AND CULTURE, 2 (3), 135–139.
31. Habibova, M. N. (2022). EVALUATIVE OBSERVATION ON DH LAWRENCE'S EPISTOLARY ACHIEVEMENT. EURASIAN JOURNAL OF ACADEMIC RESEARCH, 2 (4), 489–494.
32. Habibova, M. (2022). THEORIES OF INTERTEXTUALITY AND THE BASIC FRAMEWORK OF KRISTEVA'S FORMULATION OF HER THEORY OF INTERTEXTUALITY. Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture, 2(5), 301-307.
33. Habibova, Manzila Nuriddinovna (2022). A BIOGRAPHY IS A SPECIALIZED FORM OF HISTORY AND BASIC TYPES OF BIOGRAPHIES. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2 (5), 495-503.

34. Habibova, M. N. (2022). Epistolary Novel as a Scientific Problem. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 211–214. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1575>
35. Habibova, M. N. (2022). The Epistolary Form and Art in Modernist Literature. American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research, 3(10), 206–210. Retrieved from <https://www.grnjournals.us/index.php/ajshr/article/view/1574>
36. Habibova, M. . (2022). WRITING THE NOVEL OF LETTERS AND THE ANALYSIS OF LETTER FICTION AND DIARY FICTION. International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology, 2(11), 260–264. Retrieved from <https://researchcitations.com/index.php/ibast/article/view/317>
37. Habibova, M. . (2022). EPISTOLARY NARRATOLOGY AND CITATIONS FROM AN EPISTOLARY SOURCE: SAMUEL RICHARDSON'S PAMELA AND CLARISSA AND FRANCES BURNEY'S EVELINA. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 2(12), 1131–1135. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/6655>
38. Manzila Nuriddinovna Khabibova. (2022). JOYCE'S DEVELOPMENT AS AN AUTHOR AND HIS EXPERIMENTS WITH THE EPISTOLARY FORM. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 2(11), 73–81. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume02Issue11-10>
39. Manzila Nuriddinovna Habibova. (2022). LETTER WRITING AS ALLEGORY FOR THE WOMAN WRITER. American Journal Of Philological Sciences, 2(11), 88–92. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ajps/Volume02Issue11-12>
40. Habibova, M. N. . (2023). Origins of the Epistolary Novel and the Principal Epistolary Works. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND APPLIED LINGUISTICS, 2(2), 70–74. Retrieved from <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJLLAL/article/view/1159>
41. Khabibova, M. N. . (2023). The Historical Influence of the Epistolary Novel. INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF LANGUAGE LEARNING AND APPLIED LINGUISTICS, 2(2), 75–79. Retrieved from <https://inter-publishing.com/index.php/IJLLAL/article/view/1161>
42. Habibova, M. (2023). SPECIFIC POSSIBILITIES WRITING TECHNIQUES USED IN EPISTOLARY FORM AND THEIR EFFECTS ON BOTH THE CHARACTERS AND READERS. Eurasian Journal of Academic Research, 3(5), 172–177. Retrieved from <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/14085>
43. Habibova, M. (2023). EPISTOLARY COMPARISONS AND TRENDS. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 3(5 Part 4), 330–338. извлечено от <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/16170>
44. Habibova, M. (2023). PRAGMATICS AND COGNITION. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(10), 90-96.
45. Manzila Nuriddinovna Habibova. (2023). THE CONCEPT OF THE WHITE MAN'S SUPERIORITY AND THE PORTRAYAL OF THE ARABIC CHARACTERS IN "THE LAWRENCE OF ARABIA" AND "THE SEVEN PILLARS OF WISDOM". Academia Repository, 4(10), 24–31. Retrieved from <https://academiarepo.org/index.php/1/article/view/96>
46. Habibova, M. N. (2023). Letter Fiction and Diary Fiction. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 153–158. Retrieved from <http://grnjournal.us/index.php/AJPDIS/article/view/1386>
47. Habibova, M. N. (2023). Women and the Epistolary Novel. American Journal of Science on Integration and Human Development (2993-2750), 1(9), 119-124.